

Singular Third-Order Multipoint Boundary Value Problem at Resonance

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ABSTRACT

The present paper is particularly exhibits about the derive results of a third-order singular multipoint boundary value problem at resonance using coincidence degree arguments.

Keywords: *The present paper is particularly exhibits about the derive results of a third-order singular multipoint boundary value problem at resonance using coincidence degree arguments.*

INTRODUCTION

This paper derive the existence for the third-order singular multipoint boundary value problem at resonance of the form

$$u''' = g(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t)) + h(t)$$

$$u'(0) = 0, u''(0) = 0,$$

$$u(1) = \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j u(\zeta_{ij}),$$

Where $g : [0,1] \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is caratheodory's function (i.e., for each $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ the function $g(\cdot, u, v)$ is measurable on $[0,1]$; for almost everywhere $t \in [0,1]$, the function $g(t, \cdot, \cdot)$ is continuous on $\mathbb{R}^2$). Let $\zeta_{ij} \in (0,1), i, j = 1, 2, \dots, m-3$, and $\sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j = 1$, where g and h have singularity at $t=1$.

In [1] Gupta et al. studied the above equation when g and h have no singularity and $\sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \neq 1$. They obtained existence of a $C^1[0,1]$ solution by utilizing

Letay-Schauder continuation principle. These results correspond to the nonresonance case. The scope of this article is therefore to obtained the survive results when $\sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j = 1$ (the resonance case) and when g and h have a singularity at $t = 1$.

Definition 1

Let U and W be real Banach spaces. One says that the linear operator $L: \text{dom } L \subset U \rightarrow W$ is a **Fredholm mapping of index zero** if $\text{Ker } L$ and $W/\text{Im } L$ are of finite dimension, where $\text{Im } L$ denotes the image of L .

Note

We will require the continuous projections $P: U \rightarrow U, Q: W \rightarrow W$ such that $\text{Im } P = \text{Ker } L, \text{Ker } Q = \text{Im } L, U = \text{Ker } L \oplus \text{Ker } P, W = \text{Im } L \oplus \text{Im } Q, L|_{\text{dom } L \cap \text{Ker } P} : \text{dom } L \cap \text{ker } P \rightarrow \text{Im } L$ is an isomorphism.

Definition 2

Let L be a Fredholm mapping of index zero and Ω a bounded open subset of U such that $\text{dom } L \cap \Omega \neq \phi$. The map $M: U \rightarrow W$ is called **L -compact on $\bar{\Omega}$** , if the map $QN(\bar{\Omega})$ is bounded and $R_P(I - Q)$ is compact, where one denotes by $R_P : \text{Im } L \rightarrow \text{dom } L \cap \text{Ker } P$ the generalized inverse of L . In addition M is L -completely continuous if it L -compact on every bounded $\Omega \subset U$.

Theorem 1

Let L be a Fredholm operator of index zero and let N be L -compact on $\bar{\Omega}$. Assume that the following conditions are satisfied :

- (i) $Lu \neq \kappa Mu$ for every $(u, \kappa) \in [(dom L \setminus Ker L) \cap \partial\kappa] \times (0, 1)$.
- (ii) $Mu \notin Im L$, for every $u \in Ker L \cap \partial\kappa$.
- (iii) $deg(QM|_{Ker L \cap \partial\kappa}, \kappa \cap Ker L, 0) \neq 0$,

with $Q: W \rightarrow W$ being a continuous projection such that $Ker Q = Im L$. then the equation $Lu = Mu$ has at least one solution in $dom L \cap \bar{\Omega}$.

Proof :

We shall make use of the following classical spaces, $C[0,1], C^1[0,1], C^2[0,1], L^1[0,1], L^2[0,1]$,

and $L^\infty[0,1]$. Let $AC[0,1]$ denote the space of all absolute continuous functions on $[0,1]$, $AC^1[0,1] = \{u \in C^2[0,1] : u''(t) \in AC[0,1]\}$, $L^1_{loc}[0,1] = \{u: u|_{[0,d]} \in L^1[0,1]\}$ for every compact interval $[0, d] \subseteq [0,1]$.

$$AC_{loc}[0,1] = \{u: u|_{[0,d]} \in AC[0,1]\}.$$

Let U be the Banach space defined by

$$U = \{u \in L^1_{loc}[0,1] : (1 - t^2)u(t) \in L^1[0,1]\},$$

With the norm

$$\|v\|_u = \int_0^1 (1 - t^2) |v(t)| dt.$$

Let U be the Banach space

$$U = \{u \in C^2[0,1] : u \in C[0,1], \lim_{t \rightarrow 1^-} (1 - t^2) u'' \text{ exists}\},$$

With the norm

$$\|u\|_u = \max \left\{ \|u\|_\infty, \|(1 - t^2)u''(t)\|_\infty \right\}. \tag{1}$$

Where $\|u\|_\infty = \sup_{t \in [0,1]} |u(t)|$.

We denote the norm in $L^1[0,1]$ by $\|\cdot\|_1$. we define the linear operator $L: dom L \subset U \rightarrow W$ by

$$Lu = u'''(t), \tag{2}$$

Where

$$dom L = \left\{ u \in U : u'(0) = 0, u''(0) = 0, u(1) = \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j u(\zeta_j) \right\}$$

And $M: U \rightarrow W$ is defined by

$$Lu = g(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t)) + h(t). \tag{3}$$

Then boundary value problem (1) can be written as

$$Lu = Nu.$$

Therefore $L = N$.

Lemma

If $\sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j = 1$ then

- (i) $Ker L = \{u \in dom L : u(t) = c, c \in \mathbb{R}, t \in [0,1]\}$;
- (ii) $Im L = \left\{ v \in Z : \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds = 0 \right\}$
- (iii) $L: dom L \subset U \rightarrow W$ is a Fredholm operator

$Q: W \rightarrow W$ can be defined by

$$Qv = \frac{e^t}{h} \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds, \tag{4}$$

Where

$$h = \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j [e + \zeta_i + \zeta_j - e^{\zeta_i} - e^{\zeta_j} - 1]$$

- (iv) The linear operator $R_p: Im L \rightarrow dom L \cap Ker P$ can be defined as

$$R_p = \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho \tag{5}$$

- (v) $\|R_p v\|_U \leq \|v\|_W$ for all $v \in W$.

Proof :

- (i) It is obvious that $Ker L = \{u \in dom L : u(t) = c, c \in \mathbb{R}\}$.

(ii) We show that

$$Im L = \left\{ \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds = 0 \right\}. \quad (7)$$

$$w(t) = w(0) + \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds,$$

Where $v \in Z$

$$w'''(t) = v(t) \quad (12)$$

To do this, we consider the problem

$$w'''(t) = v(t) \quad (8)$$

(iii) For $v \in Z$, we define the projection Qv as

$$Qv = \frac{e^t}{h} \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds, \quad t \in [0,1], \quad (13)$$

And we show that (5) has a solution $w(t)$ satisfying

$$w''(0) = 0, w'(0) = 0, w(t) = \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j w(\zeta_i \zeta_j)$$

Where

$$h = \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j [e + \zeta_i + \zeta_j - e^{\zeta_i} - e^{\zeta_j} - 1] \neq 0.$$

If and only if

$$\bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds = 0 \quad (9)$$

We show that $Q: W \rightarrow W$ is well defined and bounded.

$$|Qv(t)| \leq \frac{|e^t|}{|h|} \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} |a_i| |b_j| \int_0^1 (1-s)^2 |v(s)| ds$$

Suppose (3) has a solmution $w(t)$ satisfying

$$w''(0) = 0, w'(0) = 0, w(t) = \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j w(\zeta_i \zeta_j)$$

$$= \frac{1}{|h|} \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} |a_i| |b_j| \|v\|_W |e^t|$$

Then we obtain from (5) that

$$w(t) = w(0) + \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds, \quad (10)$$

$$\|Qv\|_W \leq \int_0^1 (1-t)^2 |Qv(t)| dt$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{|h|} \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} |a_i| |b_j| \|v\|_W |e^t| \int_0^1 (1-s)^2 ds$$

And applying the boundary conditions we get

$$\bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds = \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds, \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{1}{|h|} \bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} |a_i| |b_j| \|v\|_W |e^t|_W.$$

In addition it is easily verified that

$$Q^2 v = Qv, v \in W. \quad (14)$$

Since $\bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j = 1$, and using (i) and we get

$$\bigvee_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds = 0$$

We therefore conclude that $Q: W \rightarrow W$ is a projection. If $v \in Im L$, then from (6) $Qv(t) = 0$. Hence $Im L \subseteq Ker Q$. Let $v_1 = v - Qv$; that is, $v_1 \in Ker Q$. Then

On the other hand if (6) holds, let $u_0 \in \mathbb{R}$; then

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v_1(\varrho) d\varrho ds \\ &= \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds \\ & - \frac{1}{h} \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds \end{aligned}$$

Here $h = 0$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v_1(\varrho) d\varrho ds \\ &= \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-3} a_i b_j \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho ds \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $v_1 = v$.

Thus $v_1 \in Im L$ and therefore $Ker Q \subseteq Im L$ and hence

$$W = Im L + Im Q = Im L + \mathbb{R}.$$

It follows that since $Im L \cap \mathbb{R} = \{0\}$, then $W = Im L \oplus Im Q$.

Therefore,

$$\dim Ker L = \dim Im Q = \dim \mathbb{R} = codim Im L = 1.$$

This implies that L is Fredholm mapping of index zero.

(iv) We define $P : W \rightarrow W$ by

$$Pu = u(0), \tag{15}$$

And clearly P is continuous and linear and $P^2u = P(Pu) = Pu(0) = u(0) = Pu$ and $Ker P = \{u \in U : u(0) = 0\}$. We now show that the generalized inverse $K_p = Im L \rightarrow dom L \cap Ker P$ of L is given by

$$R_p v = \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s v(\varrho) d\varrho \tag{16}$$

For $v \in Im L$ we have

$$(LR_p)v(t) = [(R_p v)(t)]'' = v(t) \tag{17}$$

And for $u \in dom L \cap Ker P$ we know that

$$\begin{aligned} (R_p L) u(t) &= \int_{\zeta_i}^1 \int_{\zeta_j}^1 \int_0^s u''(\varrho) d\varrho ds \\ &= \int_0^t (t-s)u'' ds \tag{18} \end{aligned}$$

$$= u(t) - u'(0)t - u(0) = u(t)$$

Since $u \in dom L \cap Ker P, u(0) = 0$, and $Pu = 0$.

This shows that $R_p = (L|_{dom L \cap Ker P})^{-1}$.

$$\begin{aligned} (v) \quad \|R_p v\|_{\infty} &\leq \max_{t \in [0,1]} \int_0^t (t-s)^2 |v(s)| ds \\ &\leq \int_0^t (t-s)^2 |v(s)| ds \\ &\leq \|v\|_W. \end{aligned}$$

We conclude that

$$\|R_p v\|_W \leq \|v\|_W.$$

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